

An Epidemiological Study on Gynaecological Malignancies among the Patients Attending the Out-Patient Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, JNKTMCH, Madhepura, Bihar

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Abstract

Background: To determine the epidemiological traits of patients with gynaecological malignancies in relation to gynaecological cancer risk, a cross-sectional observational study was conducted.

Methods: Patients having indicative signs of gynaecological malignancies were screened in the gynaecology out-patient department at JNKTMCH, Obstetrics and Gynecology, Madhepura, Bihar. Interviews were conducted with 113 patients who had gynaecological cancers that had been histopathologically verified.

Results: The age range for more than two-thirds of the cases (69.0%) was between 35 and 64, and the same percentage of patients came from rural areas. The majority of the patients (96.5%) had never been married. A majority (54.9%) were illiterate or only literate. Parity 3 or above was reached by nearly two-thirds (64.6%). Along with the three patients who had histories of STD syndromes from their husbands, 94.4% (17) of the 18 patients with histories of the husband's various sexual partners also had cervical cancer. No one had revealed her husband's history of condom use. The majority of patients (91.1%) utilised used or old pieces of cloth when they were menstruating.

Conclusion: Women and the general public need to be made more aware of the various epidemiological factors that may contribute to an elevated risk of gynaecological cancers.

Keywords: Gynecological Malignancies, Women - Epidemiological Characteristics, Cancer Risk - Awareness – India

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Introduction

In the underdeveloped countries, gynaecological malignancy is a significant issue for public health. The main issues in this regard are the lack of community knowledge of cancer, the hazy epidemiology, the erratic pathology, and the absence of adequate screening facilities. Early diagnosis of these tumours and rapid implementation of treatment can prevent the bad outcomes that come with delayed presentation of cases. Therefore, there is a greater need for focus on cancer prevention and early detection.

As a major public health problem, more than 80% of the cervical cancer cases occur in the developing countries [1] and it tends to present about 15 years earlier than it does in the developed countries. It is therefore postulated that a more aggressive variant of the disease probably occurs in this environment. Many cases remain undiagnosed. Other peculiar negative trends observed are late presentation and resultant very low five-year survival data. WHO estimates that the contribution of cervical cancer to adult female death is 35% [2].

The highest rates of cervical cancer in South-Central Asia by age-standardized incidence (30.7 per 100,000) and mortality (17.4 per 100,000) are found in India [3] Of all gynaecological cancers, ovarian cancer has the highest fatality-to-case ratio [4] and it is particularly significant for public health [5]. However, endometrial carcinoma and vulval/vaginal cancer are frequently found in elderly women, considerably increasing mortality. The same authors have claimed in past works that in developing nations like India, low awareness of certain malignancies and patients' health care seeking behaviour considerably increase this burden [6].

Materials and Methods

The Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at the Tertiary Care Jannayak Karpuri Thakur Medical College and

Hospital in Madhepura, Bihar, where this hospital-based cross-sectional observational study was done. The programme included newly registered patients with gynaecological morbidity of varying severity who visited the gynaecology out-patient department for two years, from November 2020 to October 2022.

An estimated 50% of these patients, or 9829, were proposed to be selected for the study, with random selection of the first patient and then every alternate patient. This was done because the expected number of patients with gynaecological morbidity during the study period, based on the prior records, was roughly 19658. Nevertheless, during the research period, 9829 patients may have been covered.

Study Tools

1. A pre-designed and pre-tested checklist and a pre-designed and pre-tested schedule,
2. Hospital records,
3. Past health records of the patients,
4. Investigation reports, particularly histopathology reports,
5. Cusco's bivalve self-retaining vaginal speculum,
6. Stethoscope and sphygmomanometer.

Study Technique

1. Interview method,
2. Clinical examination.

Before beginning the study on 10 patients, the checklist and timetable underwent pre-testing in the gynaecology outpatient clinic of the same hospital. As a result, any necessary revisions were made and these were then finalised. As stated, a visit to the gynaecological outpatient clinic was made. Patients who had symptoms that might point to gynaecological cancers were screened out. Patients were only included if they had at least two suspicious symptoms. Contact bleeding, irregular, heavy, or protracted

vaginal bleeding, postmenopausal bleeding, excessive, offensive, with or without blood tinged vaginal discharge, lump in the belly, abdominal distension or discomfort, and vulval development were the signs taken into consideration for screening. All of the eligible patients gave their informed consent to take part in the study and agreed to cooperate with the required physical examination and investigations. For the purpose of confirming the diagnosis, necessary tests and investigations, particularly histopathological analysis, were conducted. The programme was used for patients with histopathologically confirmed gynaecological cancers, while the checklist was utilised for screening. The schedule was divided into a few sections, including general information, a thorough medical history (including menstrual history and menstrual hygiene), obstetrical, medical, surgical, family, and personal histories), presenting symptoms, clinical examination findings, histopathological examination reports, and a definitive diagnosis with FIGO staging of gynaecological malignancies.

Finally, an in-depth interview was conducted to assess knowledge of gynaecological malignancies and health care seeking behaviour.

When necessary, the collected data were compiled and statistically evaluated using basic proportions and the chi-square test. Few occurrences of gynaecological malignancies without the indicative symptoms would have gone unnoticed since the study population was weeded out in order to detect potential cases of gynaecological malignancies based on certain symptoms. Only individuals were included who consented to take part in the study. It is important to be cautious when extrapolating the results of this study to the community's entire population of women with gynaecological cancers.

Results

483 individuals (22.6%) of the 9829 gynaecology outpatients over the research period had symptoms that might indicate gynaecological malignancies. Six patients (0.3%) were unfollowable. As a result, a total of 477 cases (22.3%) could be further examined, and histology was able to validate each patient's diagnosis. Finally, 113 patients' diagnoses were finally determined to be gynaecological cancers (5.3%), with cervical malignancy being the most prevalent (70 out of 113 patients; 61.9%), followed by ovarian malignancy (27 out of 113 patients; 23.9%).

Table 1: Distribution of Patients with Gynecological Malignancies According to Socio-Demographic Characteristics (n =113)

Characteristics	Cervix (n=70)	Ovary (n=27)	Endometrium (n=6)	Vulva (n=2)	Vagina (n=2)	GTN (n=6)	Total (n=113)
Age (years)							
• ≤19	-	2(7)	-	-	-	1(17)	3(3)
• 20-34	8(11)	6(22)	-	1(50)	1(50)	3(50)	19(17)
• 35-49	28(40)	10(37)	2(33)	1(50)	1(50)	1(17)	43(38)
• 50-64	26(37)	6(22)	2(33)	-	-	1(17)	35(31)
• ≥65	8(11)	3(11)	2(33)	-	-	-	13(12)
Religion							
• Hindu	67(96)	22(82)	6(100)	2(100)	2(100)	6(100)	105(93)
• Muslim	3(4)	5(19)	-	-	-	-	8(7)
Place of Residence	51(73)	16(59)	2(33)	2(100)	1(50)	6(100)	78(69)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural • Urban 	19(27)	11(41)	4(67)	-	1(50)	-	35(31)
Marital status							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Married • Single • Widow 	46(66)	17(63)	3(50)	2(100)	2(100)	6(100)	76(67)
	1(1)	3(11)	-	-	-	-	4(4)
	23(33)	7(26)	3(50)	-	-	-	33(29)
Literacy status							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illiterate • Literate • Primary • Middle • Secondary 	37(53)	11(41)	2(33)	1(50)	-	-	51(45)
	7(10)	1(4)	2(33)	-	-	1(17)	11(10)
	12(17)	2(7)	-	-	2(100)	1(17)	17(15)
	7(10)	7(26)	2(33)	1(50)	-	3(50)	20(18)
	7(10)	6(22)	-	-	-	1(17)	14(12)
PCI of Family (Rs/month)							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <400 • ≥400 	33(47)	15(56)	2(33)	1(50)	1(50)	3(50)	55(49)
	37(53)	12(44)	4(67)	1(50)	1(50)	3(50)	58(51)

Table 2: Distribution of Patients with Gynecological Malignancies According to Reproductive Characteristics (n =113)

Characteristics	Cervix (n=70)	Ovary (n=27)	Endometrium (n=6)	Vulva (n=2)	Vagina (n=2)	GTN (n=6)	Total (n=113)
Parity							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 • 1 • 2 • 3 • ≥4 	1(1)	5(19)	2(33)	-	-	2(33)	10(9)
	2(3)	2(7)	-	-	-	1(17)	5(4)
	12(17)	9(33)	-	1(50)	1(50)	2(33)	25(22)
	14(20)	4(15)	2(33)	1(50)	1(50)	-	22(20)
	41(59)	7(26)	2(33)	-	-	1(17)	51(45)
Total	70(100)	27(100)	6(100)	2(100)	2(100)	6(100)	113(100)
Mean±SD	4.1±1.9	3.0±3.0	2.3±1.9	2.5±0.7	2.5±0.7	2.3±3.4	3.6±2.3
Age at marriage (yrs.)							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 10-14 • 15-19 • 20-24 • ≥25 	24(35)	7(29)	-	1(50)	-	1(17)	33(30)
	42(61)	11(46)	5(83)	1(50)	2(100)	4(67)	65(60)
	3(4)	3(13)	1(17)	-	-	1(17)	8(7)
	-	3(13)	-	-	-	-	3(3)
Total	69(100)	24(100)	6(100)	2(100)	2(100)	6(100)	109(100)
Mean±SD	15±2.6	17±4.9	18±2.0	16±4.2	18±0.7	17±2.6	16±3.3
Age of 1 st child birth							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ≤14 • 15-19 • 20-24 • ≥25 	6(9)	2(9)	-	-	-	1(25)	9(9)
	43(62)	12(55)	2(50)	1(50)	1(50)	2(50)	61(59)
	20(29)	4(18)	2(50)	1(50)	1(50)	1(25)	29(28)
	-	4(18)	-	-	-	-	4(4)
Total	69(100)	22(100)	4(100)	2(100)	2(100)	4(100)	103(100)
Mean±SD	18±2.6	20±4.8	20±0.6	18±3.5	19±1.4	18±2.5	18±3.2

Table 3: Distribution of Patients with Gynecological Malignancies According to Behavioral and Lifestyle Characteristics (n =113)

Characteristics	Cervix (n=70)	Ovary (n=27)	Endometrium (n=6)	Vulva (n=2)	Vagina (n=2)	GTN (n=6)	Total (n=113)
Tobacco Chewing	19(27)	7(26)	2(33)	1(50)	1(50)	-	30(27)
Exposure to Passive smoking	48(69)	11(41)	3(50)	2(100)	2(100)	2(33)	68(60)
Contraceptive Practice	30(43)	9(33)	3(50)	2(100)	1(50)	3(50)	48(43)
Material used for Menstrual Hygiene Practice							
• Sanitary Pad	4(6)	4(15)	-	-	-	1(17)	9(8)
• New Cloth	3(4)	1(4)	1(17)	-	1(50)	-	6(5)
• Old/Reused Cloth	66(94)	22(85)	6(100)	2(100)	1(50)	5(83)	102(91)
Relation to Husband							
• H/O Multiple Sexual Partners of the Husband	17(25)	-	1(17)	-	-	-	18(17)
• H/O of STD Syndrome of the Husband	3(4)	-	-	-	-	-	3(3)

Table 4: Distribution of Patients with Gynecological Malignancies According to other epidemiological Characteristics (n =113)

Characteristics	Cervix (n=70)	Ovary (n=27)	Endometrium (n=6)	Vulva (n=2)	Vagina (n=2)	GTN (n=6)	Total (n=113)
H/o of associated medical condition	12(17)	6(22)	5(83)	-	-	-	23(20)
Past history suggestive of RTI	21(30)	6(22)	4(67)	-	1(50)	1(17)	33(29)
Past history of gynecological surgery	29(41)	13(48)	2(33)	-	2(100)	6(100)	52(46)
Family history of malignancy	11(16)	5(19)	-	1(50)	-	1(17)	18(16)

Discussion

The goal of this study is to determine the epidemiological traits of the patients in connection to the risk of gynaecological cancer in India. The most frequent gynaecological cancer found in this study

was cervical malignancy (61.9%), which was followed by ovarian malignancy (23.9%). The patients with gynaecological malignancies were an average age of 45.8 years old. Patients with endometrial cancer

and cervical cancer have been reported to have mean ages of 48.1 and 53, respectively, which are older than patients with other gynaecological malignancies. The mean age of patients with ovarian cancer, however, is lower (43.3 years) than that of those with gynaecological malignancies. According to Chhabra *et al* [7] between the ages of 35 and 49, nearly half (44.6%) of instances of gynaecological cancer occurred. The average age of cases of cervical cancer was 45.7 years, and instances of ovarian cancer mostly affected those between the ages of 35 and 49.

The majority of patients (92.9%) in the current study with gynaecological malignancies were Hindus, and the majority of patients (69.0%) were from rural areas. Hindus made up nearly all of the cervical cancer patients (95.7%). Two Indian investigations provide strong support for these findings (Chhabra *et al.*, Sharma *et al.*). 7.8 It should be noted that most patients in India's government-run tertiary care facilities come from rural areas with poor socioeconomic status. This was brought up in a previous paper by the authors (Sarkar *et al.*) [9]

Kidanto *et al* [10]. study in Tanzania, which confirms the current study's finding that the majority of cervical cancer patients (62.9%) were illiterate or only literate, provides more evidence for this observation. Education level and the percentage of patients with gynaecological malignancies were not found to be significantly correlated in the current study, but the same authors reported in an earlier paper that the time to presentation at a tertiary care hospital after the onset of symptoms decreased with increasing educational level of the patients (Sarkar *et al.*) [9] making the management of the disease easier.

With a range of Rs. 100 - 2500, the median and mean PCI costs for the patients' families were Rs. 400 and Rs. 543, respectively. The

mean PCI of the patients' families in this study is about one-fourth of the figure for India. Many low-income women might not have easy access to quality medical treatment, which could cause them to show up later than necessary at a healthcare facility.

No clear correlation between reproductive traits and the percentage of patients with endometrial cancer, vulvar/vaginal cancer, and GTN has been established in this study. However, a correlation between reproductive traits and the percentage of patients with cervical cancer may exist. With rising parity, the percentage of patients with cervical cancer rose.

The majority of patients with gynaecological malignancies in the current study were multiparous, which is consistent with studies conducted in other regions of the world. Studies from underdeveloped nations and the findings of the current study suggest that individuals with ovarian cancer may also be multiparous, just like those with cervical cancer. However, a research conducted in Ireland by Daly *et al.* discovered that the mean parity of patients with ovarian cancer was lower (1.9) [11] Ovarian cancer is more frequent in nulliparous people, according to medical literature (Dutta *et al*) [12].

The majority of the 109 "ever-married" patients with gynaecological cancers had an early marriage. This finding holds true for cases of cervical cancer as well, which is consistent with research by Sharma *et al* [8] and Kidanto *et al* [10] According to a 2004 health study from Hong Kong (Department of Health, Government of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region), women who engage in sexual activity early in life have a higher chance of developing cervical cancer than women who engage in sexual activity later in life. The early marriage is a predisposing factor for cervical cancer, according to the current study.

The majority of the 103 patients with gynaecological malignancies were young mothers who had just had their first child. However, ovarian cancer affected all four of the patients who were ≥ 25 years old at the time of their first births. In their study carried out in Sweden, Mogren *et al* [13] noted that growing maternal age at the time of the first birth was linked to an increased risk of endometrial and ovarian cancers and a lower risk of cervical cancer.

A sizable majority (60.9%) of individuals who were current, frequent smokers also had cervical cancer. Contrary to Sharma *et al* [8] study, which was conducted in India and found that only 6% of patients with cervical malignancy had a history of chewing tobacco, a sizable fraction (27.2%) of patients with cervical malignancy did. This discrepancy in results could be brought about by variations in the study's setting, population, and methods. The majority of patients (60.2%) with gynaecological malignancies had a history of passive smoking exposure; for cervical malignancies, this percentage was 68.6%. A health report from Hong Kong (Department of Health, Government of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region, 2004) that found that exposure to environmental tobacco smoke raised the risk for cervical neoplasia lends additional weight to this conclusion.

The usage of contraceptives was reported by just under half of all patients with gynaecological cancers. About 25% of the patients have undergone sterilisation surgery. More over half of the patients with a history of ever using oral contraceptives had cervical cancer. These results closely match those of the Indian study by Chhabra *et al* [7] which revealed that sterilisation was the most popular form of birth control among patients with gynaecological cancers. Other forms of birth control have barely ever been employed, and recorded use of barrier contraceptives was nearly nonexistent.

Chhabra *et al* [7] could not discover any patients who reported ever using oral contraceptives, in contrast to the current study where 16.8% of patients had. In the study conducted by Were and Buziba [14] only 22% of cervical cancer patients had ever used a contraceptive, as opposed to 42.9% in the current study.

When menstruating, the majority of patients (91.1%) with gynaecological malignancies and 94.3% of patients with cervical malignancies utilised worn-out or recycled pieces of clothing. One of the key elements of menstruation hygiene is the type of material used, which is also an important aspect of menstrual practise. This was said by the same author in prior writing (Dasgupta & Sarkar *et al*) [15]

94.4% of patients with a history of their spouses having several sexual partners and 100% of patients with a history of STD syndrome in their husbands both had cervical cancer. The husbands of cases had noticeably more sexual partners than the husbands of controls in the majority of studies, according to the health report from Hong Kong (Department of Health, Government of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region, 2004), which discussed the role of the male in the causation of cervical cancer. Cervical cancer seldom affects sexually inactive women, although it is strongly associated with early sexual activity with several partners. One of the most prevalent sexually transmitted diseases, the human papillomavirus (HPV), is present in almost all women with aggressive cervical cancer (Walboomers *et al*) [16].

Only 29.2% of patients with gynaecological cancers had previously experienced RTI-suggestive symptoms. They noted abnormal vaginal discharge as the most frequent symptom (100.0%). The same author has said that abnormal vaginal discharge is frequently found in RTI (Dasgupta & Sarkar) [15] and

that poor menstrual hygiene is a significant risk factor for this condition (Dasgupta & Sarkar). [15] The most prevalent presenting symptom of gynaecological malignancies, according to the same investigators, is abnormal vaginal discharge (Sarkar *et al.*) [9].

In total, 18 patients with gynaecological malignancies (15.9%) disclosed a family history of any cancer. Such a history was present in five patients (18.5%) with ovarian cancer. This supports a study by Malik [17] from Pakistan, where 20% of epithelial ovarian cancer patients reported a positive family history of cancer. 12.5% of the patients in a related study conducted in India by Nigam *et al* [18] disclosed a family history of cancer. However, just one patient with ovarian cancer (4.8%) had a positive family history of cancer, according to Odukogbe *et al* [19].

Conclusion

According to the results of the current study, gynaecological malignancies may be affected by factors other than family history, including location, marital status, female literacy, socioeconomic status, parity, age at first childbirth, age at first marriage, use of contraception, menstrual hygiene, habit of chewing tobacco, exposure to passive smoking, etc. Additionally, the husband's sexual behaviour is a cause for concern. In this context, increasing female awareness is crucial, and initiatives including female literacy, the media, health professionals, primary care physicians, volunteer health promoters, etc. may be fruitful. The sickness should also be made known to other family members, such as husbands, and the larger community. To further understand the epidemiological variables for various gynaecological cancers, case control studies should be conducted. In order to gain more knowledge about gynaecological cancers' early identification and prevention,

community research should be conducted in the future.

References

1. Sankaranarayanan R, Ferlay J. Worldwide burden of gynaecological cancer: The size of the problem. *Best Pract Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol*, 2006; 20: 207-25.
2. Ayinde OA, Omigbodun AO, Ilesanmi AO. Awareness of Cervical Cancer, Papanicolaou's Smear and Its Utilisation among Female Undergraduates in Ibadan. *Afr J Reprod Health*, 2004;8: 68-80.
3. Ferlay J, Bray F, Pisani P, Parkin DM. GLOBOCAN 2002: Cancer Incidence, Mortality and Prevalence Worldwide. IARC Cancer Base No. 5, version 2.0. Lyon: IARC Press. 2004.
4. Berek JS. Novak's Gynecology, Thirteenth Edition. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins. 2002.
5. Laurvick CL, Semmens JB, Holman CD, Leung YC. Ovarian cancer in Western Australia (1982-98): incidence, mortality and survival. *Aust N Z J Public Health*, 2003;27: 588-95.
6. Sarkar M, Konar H, Raut DK. Knowledge and health care-seeking behavior in relation to gynecological malignancies in India: A study of the patients with gynecological malignancies in a tertiary care hospital of Kolkata. *J Cancer Educ*, 2011; 26: 348-54.
7. Chhabra S, Sonak M, Prem V, Sharma S. Gynaecological malignancies in a rural institute in India. *J Obstet Gynaecol*, 2002; 22: 426-9.
8. Sharma R, Maheshwari V, Aftab M, Das BC. Role of different epidemiological factors, colposcopy and cytology in the screening of cervical cancer in symptomatic patients. *Indian J Med Res*, 2005; 121: 109-10.
9. Sarkar M, Konar H, Raut DK. Knowledge and health care-seeking behavior in relation to gynecological

- malignancies in India: A study of the patients with gynecological malignancies in a tertiary care hospital of Kolkata. *J Cancer Educ*, 2011; 26: 348-54.
10. Kidanto HL, Kilewo CD, Moshiro C. Cancer of the cervix: knowledge and attitudes of female patients admitted at Muhimbili National Hospital, Dar es Salaam. *East Afr Med J*, 2002; 79: 467-75.
 11. Daly C, Fitzpatrick R, Murphy H. Ovarian cancer in a county hospital. *Ir Med J*, 1989; 82: 60-1.
 12. Dutta DC. Text Book of Gynaecology including contraception, Fourth Edition. Calcutta: New Central Book Agency (P) Ltd. 2003.
 13. Mogren I, Stenlund H, Hogberg U. Long-term impact of reproductive factors on the risk of cervical, endometrial, ovarian and breast cancer. *Acta Oncol*, 2001; 40: 849-54.
 14. Were EO, Buziba NG. Presentation and health care seeking behaviour of patients with cervical cancer seen at Moi Teaching and Referral Hospital, Eldoret, Kenya. *East Afr Med J*, 2001; 78: 55-9.
 15. Dasgupta A, Sarkar M. Menstrual hygiene: how hygienic is the adolescent girl? *Indian J Community Med*, 2008; 33: 77-80.
 16. Walboomers JM, Jacobs MV, Manos MM, et al. Human papillomavirus is a necessary cause of invasive cervical cancer worldwide. *J Pathol*, 1999; 189: 12-9.
 17. Malik IA. A prospective study of clinicopathological features of epithelial ovarian cancer in Pakistan. *J Pak Med Assoc*, 2002; 52: 155-8.
 18. Nigam PK, Jain A, Goyal P, Chitra R. Role of heat-stable fraction of alkaline phosphatase as an adjunct to CA 125 in monitoring patients of epithelial ovarian carcinoma. *Indian J Clin Biochem*, 2005; 20: 43-7.
 19. Odukogbe AA, Adebamowo CA, Ola B, et al. Ovarian cancer in Ibadan: characteristics and management. *J Obstet Gynaecol*, 2004; 24: 294-7.